

International Symposium on
**Nuclear
Endocrinology**
and **Metabolic
Diseases**

Hotel Zira, Belgrade

11-12 May
2023

**ABSTRACT
BOOK**

Co-funded by the
Erasmus+ Programme
of the European Union

KLINICKI CENTAR SRBIJE

UNIVERSITET U BEOGRADU
MEDICINSKI
FAKULTET

An Unusual Case of Metastatic Functional Differentiated Thyroid Carcinoma

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Introduction: Most common causes of hyperthyroidism are subacute thyroiditis, Graves' disease and toxic adenoma, in which nuclear medicine already has a well-established role, in forms of thyroid scan and uptake, and radioiodine treatment. However, rarely, thyrotoxicosis can be caused by functionally differentiated thyroid carcinoma (DTC) and its metastasis.

Case report: Here, we report a case of a 67-year-old female patient who had been initially treated for hyperthyroidism caused by a toxic adenoma in the left lobe of the thyroid gland but remained hyperthyroid after two doses of radioactive iodine (RAI). Due to pelvic pain and low extremity weakness, the patient underwent a further evaluation with FDG PET/CT scan which discovered a soft tissue lesion in the sacrum as well as multiple bone metastases. A biopsy of the sacral mass revealed it to be a metastasis of DTC. The patient received palliative radiotherapy treatment for the sacrum lesion and total thyroidectomy (TT) was also done. Two months after TT she presented again with signs and symptoms of thyrotoxicosis. An I 131 whole body scan was performed and revealed multiple radioiodine avid lung and bone metastases, and she was subsequently treated with two cycles of radioiodine therapy (RIT). Following the administration of RIT, the patient had stable disease for the next year after which she underwent treatment utilizing the Gamma Knife for the brain metastases. The patient continued to receive sorafenib till now and she is currently in a stable condition.

Conclusion: This case highlights that unexplained thyrotoxicosis should be considered as a potential complication of metastatic disease, in which both diagnostic and therapeutic application of radioiodine can play a significant role.